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METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF USING INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

The article explores the effectiveness of using information and communication technologies in foreign language lessons. It also analyzes the peculiarities of learning a foreign language and the relevance of applying a computer in the classroom.

Key words: *effectiveness, information and communication technologies, peculiarity, formation.*

The main purpose of teaching a foreign language in higher military educational institutions is the formation and development of the communicative culture of cadets, teaching practical mastery of a foreign language. The tasks of the teacher are to activate the activities of each cadet in the learning process, to create situations for their creative activity. In modern conditions, given the great and serious interest of students in information technology, it is possible to use this opportunity as a tool for developing motivation in foreign language lessons.

The use of computer technology makes it possible to make an informed choice of the best training option. The use of a computer as a tool for working with information is very diverse and diverse. The specificity of the subject of a foreign language determines the active and appropriate use of a computer in the classroom. The leading component of the content of foreign language teaching is teaching various types of speech activity: listening, reading, writing and speaking. With the help of a computer, it is possible to solve the main linguistic and didactic tasks of teaching aspects of language, forming skills and abilities in various types of speech activity. When teaching grammar, the formation of receptive grammatical skills in reading and listening; the formation of productive grammatical skills, mainly in writing; control of

the level of grammatical skills based on test programs; provision of reference and information support (automated grammar reference books, grammatical error detection systems).

When teaching vocabulary - the formation of receptive lexical skills of reading and listening; the formation of productive lexical skills, mainly in writing; control of the level of lexical skills based on test and game computer programs using visual visualization; expansion of the vocabulary of students.

When teaching reading, the formation of skills for establishing sound-letter correspondences; teaching the technique of reading aloud; improving reading technique skills; consolidating receptive lexical and grammatical reading skills; mastering the skills of extracting semantic information of various types from the text; teaching various types of text analysis; forming the ability to independently overcome language difficulties; controlling the correctness and depth of understanding of the read text.

When teaching listening, it is the formation of phonetic listening skills; control of the correctness of understanding the listened text.

When teaching speaking, it is the formation of phonetic speaking skills; the organization of communication in pairs and small groups using role-playing games.

When teaching translation, it is the formation of lexical and grammatical translation skills; control of the correctness of the translation. Considering the issue of teaching listening and speaking in foreign language lessons, it should be noted that modern multimedia tools provide more opportunities for the development of trained skills.

Listening involves auditory perception of speech with its understanding, and speaking is characterized by productivity (reproduction) and the use of the oral form of speech. Today, teaching a foreign language with the integration of multimedia capabilities allows you to formulate listening and speaking skills in almost a real communication situation in which the foreign language being studied will later be used.

The main types of work with a personal computer in foreign language lessons can be divided into two groups: the use of educational and cognitive programs on CD and the creation of programs in various applications by the teacher himself with further use in lessons when explaining the material or when working out and checking it.

Using educational programs is the most affordable way to use a computer, both in class and outside of school hours. A variety of multimedia games contribute to the expansion of vocabulary, introduce you to the grammar of a foreign language, teach you to understand speech by ear, and write correctly.

Multimedia capabilities allow you to listen to speech in the language you are learning, and speed control allows you to split phrases into separate words. Using a microphone and automatic pronunciation control allows you to adjust your phonetic skills. In addition to using educational computer programs in foreign language lessons,

a number of didactic tasks can be solved using the Internet: to form reading skills and abilities using materials from the global network; to improve the writing skills of cadets; to replenish the vocabulary of students; to form a stable motivation to learn a language. In addition, the possibilities of Internet technologies contribute to expanding the horizons of cadets. The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The global Internet network creates conditions for obtaining any necessary information located anywhere in the world: regional studies, news from the life of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, necessary literature, etc. Cadets can take part in tests, quizzes, contests, Olympiads held on the Internet.

The 21st century is the age of informatization, making its own adjustments to the traditional teaching of a foreign language. The Internet and the computer are among those technical means of teaching foreign languages that were not invented specifically for this purpose and primarily perform other functions. However, due to their great capabilities, they attract the attention of practical teachers and methodologists.

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